

Study the Impact of Social Media on Consumer Buying Behaviour and its Effects with the Consumer of Uttarakhand State

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Abstract:- Social media is used by billions of people worldwide to connect and share information. Social media gives you the personal freedom to interact with loved ones, learn new things, explore new interests, and be entertained. Social evidence, a crucial factor in purchasing decisions, may be found proactively on social media. And over half (51%) of buyers check reviews on websites and social networks to evaluate a service or product prior purchasing it. Present paper study how social media effect the buying decision of the consumer of Uttarakhand. Like other state of India Uttarakhand is also developed in social media. Research is carried on secondary basis. How various literature show the impact of social media on consumer behaviour is pen down and conclusions are drawn to show the result of various literature

Keywords:- social media, consumer behaviour, interest, purchasing power.

I. INTRODUCTION

Social networking increasingly involves commerce as well as discussion. Social indicators have performance and improved consumer purchasing decisions, but the widespread use of cellphones and social media has elevated word-of-mouth to new levels.

Most consumers now travel with their purchasing power and posting in their pockets. Consumers no longer need to visit businesses to find new products; instead, they may find inspiration by scrolling through their social media accounts. They no longer need to call their pals for a referral; instead, they make requests on social media and solicit unrestricted feedback from close relatives, close friends, and complete strangers. This is especially accurate for the group that brands want to target the most.¹

Consumer behaviour includes both the mental and physical processes that people use to find, assess, buy, and use goods and services. Consumers trade their limited resources, including as money, time, and effort, for valuable goods in the marketplace. When researching how consumers purchase long-term care insurance, a consumer researcher may look into: (1) the characteristics of consumers who purchase this type of insurance (such as income, age, and lifestyle); (2) where they purchase it (such as from an agent vs. from an 800 number listed in an advertisement); (3) when they purchase it (such as after a critical event like a parent's illness or after seeing an advertisement); and (4)

¹(How Does Social Media Influence Consumer Behavior?, 2021)

how they purchase it (such as comparing multiple policies vs. choosing the same one) 5. why people purchase it (e.g., worry about exhausting life savings against desire for great care in old age), and 6. what transpires after they purchase it (e.g., satisfaction with the decision and the company).²

According to a report by ASSOCHAM, Uttarakhand has surpassed all other states in the nation in terms of growth in the industrial and service sectors during the past 10 years.

In research that looked at 10 years, from 2004–2005 to 2014–2015, it was found that Uttarakhand had the greatest CAGR of any state in India during that time, at 16.5% and 12.3% respectively for the industry and services sectors.

The state, which is among the smallest in the nation, performed far better than the period's 7% national average growth, according to the report.

According to the research "Uttarakhand on Expressway To Growth," the state "has achieved outstanding economic growth and industrial development as the state has recorded CAGR of over 12% throughout the aforesaid period, which is the highest among major states in India."

According to D S Rawat, national secretary general of ASSOCHAM, Uttarakhand's contribution to India's economy has also somewhat increased from just under 0.8 percent in 2004-2005 to 1.2 percent in 2013-2014.

According to him, the services sector, which comprises travel and tourism, lodging and dining, transportation, storage, communication, banking and finance, and other similar activities, accounted for 51% of the gross state domestic product (GSDP) in 2014–15, up from 49.5% in 2004–05.

"It is encouraging to note that domestic and foreign tourists' arrival in the state has picked up after it was hit by massive floods and landslides in June 2013, mostly due to swift action by the state government," said Babu Lal Jain, head of ASSOCHAM's Uttarakhand Development Task Force, which conducted the study. Tourism and hospitality are a major segment under the services sector in Uttarakhand and are also the mainstay of its economy.

But according to the ASSOCHAM report, Uttarakhand's performance in the agriculture sector and related fields shows a bleak image because its proportion of the global

²(Consumer Behavior - an Overview | ScienceDirect Topics, n.d.)

gross domestic product (GSDP) has dramatically decreased from over 22% in 2004–2005 to just over 9% in 2014–2015.

Additionally, the state's agriculture industry saw a weak CAGR of only approximately 3% between 2004–05 and 2014–15, partly as a result of sandy soils' poor ability to hold onto water for long, which lowers crop production, it claimed.

The study recommended that the government of Uttarakhand should support a separate policy for hill farming because more than 51% of the state's total workforce and roughly 67% of all rural workers rely on agriculture for a living.

The study highlights the need to improve infrastructure in the health sector despite highlighting important steps the state has taken in the infrastructure sector, such as increasing the density of roads during the time period and its high literacy rate of about 80%.³

II. OBJECTIVE

- Media provide information which affect the psychological factor of the consumer
- Social media affects the brand preference of the consumer
- Various media helps in attaining the social factors
- Media helps in changing the social factors of the consumer

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Gupta, sachin (2020) According to their study social media has a larger impact on the buying decision of the consumer. According to their quantitative research they have calculated the degree of impact of social media on the consumer. Consumer are more inclined due to social networking as advertiser are clueless about what discussion is held among the consumers. Study shows that consumer satisfaction is very much influenced by the usage of social media which effect the various stages of consumer information search their various evaluation steps. It also states that consumer satisfaction level even get convinced as the consumer reaches towards the purchasing step and with help of social media consumer can evaluate their post purchase decision⁴

Nagi, Dr.Muskan (2021) It studies the impact of social media effect on the brand choice of laptops. It was found out that consumers are gaining more information from the media along with family, friend, and company website. This new medium of information collector has made consumer choice wider. In the study preference of product name laptop is consider on the factors like battery, display, portability and many other which have been gathered from the social media. Consumer consider social networks as more convenient information collector source. Marketers use technique as discount, free coupon to attract consumer

³(Uttarakhand Tops In Industry, Service Sectors Growth, n.d.)

⁴(Gupta & Chopra, 2020)

on various platforms of social media. Social media creates mass brand awareness which help consumers and company all together. Study has attained its objective and stating clearly that there is a significant relation between the social media and consumer behaviour.⁵

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study qualitative approach is used as the data is collected from the already collected sources. The comparative study is made by studying the various research on the similar topic and then these studies are compared to extract how much is the difference and similarities between this research. Secondary data is used to make the comparison and conclusions are drawn.

V. FINDING

A. Media provide information which affect the psychological factor of the consumer

Psychological factors include the motivation of the consumer towards a product. What consumer perceived and how the consumer intentions are generated for the product. Many studies state that 88% of the consumer in the age group of 18 to 29 uses one or the other kind of social media. This study clearly states that to affect the choice of the consumer is very easy as media fluctuate the mind of the consumer very easily.⁶

One of the research states that 71% of the population buy their product by the reference given by social media. Report of marketing week.com state that 31% of the population make their buying decision from the social media. Report of deloitte clearly state that social media has increased purchases by 41%. Even 80% of the business uses social media to create brand awareness as stated by maybe tec.⁷

B. Social media affects the brand preference of the consumer

There are research available which clearly state that media does impact the brand preference of the consumer. one of the research paper study the impact of media on the sale of laptop in the market. There findings clearly state that media does impact the brand preference of the consumer. study also reveal that consumer does make research from the media before making their buying decision. By the media they get the attribute about the products and with the help of the media information they can go for brand preference⁸

Other research made on the effect of social media on brand preference state that there is a higher percentage of younger consumer which support the fact that media does affect the brand preference of the consumer. the margin between the fact that how media affect the brand or creative

⁵(Nagi& Al, 2021)

⁶(*The Psychology of Social Media*, 2019)(*The Psychology of Social Media*, 2019)⁶

⁷ ("Social Media Marketing and Consumer Psychology," 2020)

⁸Nagi& Al, 2021)

marketing affecting the brand is very low as research clearly state that media does indulge consumer in shifting their brand preference.⁹

Though all these studies state the positive impact of media on the consumer perception but there are studies which state that media cannot be helpful everytime. Irrelevant advertisement does antagonize the consumer, making them feel that they have no opinion of their own instead media is taking control of the them. Some of the advertisement does not create any motivation for the consumer to have a look on the product as those advertisement fail to create interest in the consumer.¹⁰

so, these research state that though media does affects the positive impact on the brand preference of the consumer but it do create negative impact on the consumer when unnecessary media information is given to the consumer.

C. Various media helps in attaining the social factors

Study conducted by forbes state that 81% of the consumer change their buying behaviour after seeing their friend activity on various social media post.¹¹

Even social media post of other consumer motivates around 66% of consumer in making their buying decision as stated by the reports of stackla.¹²

Another research state that 71% of the consumer get influenced by the other social media reference of their friends and family.¹³

Another study state that social media like facebook has guided around 52% of consumer in their online and offline purchases.¹⁴

D. Media helps in changing the social factors of the consumer

Research state that reference group motivate the consumer in their buying behaviour. Consumer do get influence by social media activity of their group.

Most participants do not observe the buying behaviour of referents prior to using a social commerce platform or buying a product or a service on a social commerce platform. Only a few participants mentioned that they observe the buying behaviour of their referents prior to buying a product or service on a social commerce platform, especially when the product or service is quite expensive. Most of the participants have indicated that they do not purchase the same or similar products than their reference

⁹Parmar, 2019)

¹⁰(Negative Effects Of Social Media On Consumer Behaviour | Ipl.Org, n.d.)

¹¹(Is Social Media the Biggest Influencer of Buying Decisions?, n.d.)

¹²(How Does Social Media Influence Consumer Behavior?, 2021)

¹³(Ewing, n.d.)

¹⁴(Facebook Influences Over Half Of Shoppers Says DigitasLBI's Connected Commerce Report | The Drum, n.d.)

groups in order to be more like them or to mimic their style. Only a few participants mentioned that they have, in the past, subconsciously purchased the same or similar product than that of their referent in order to copy their style or to be more like them.

Various reference group, relatives, role in the society, status and many more are the element which also affect the buying behaviour of the consumer.

VI. CONCLUSION

So, it is evident from the research that social media does affect the buying behaviour of the consumer. Media like television, radio, internet and various blogs have open up the places for advertising which has leads the consumer in confusion to decide upon which product to buy. Marketer has varied opportunity to explore the mindset of the consumer. media has so much affected the decision of the consumer that consumer often end in buying the product which are more advertised as compared to what they want. Uttarakhand state has been emerging as a new developed market for consumer. Like every other state of India Uttarakhand is also blooming and making its mark in the retail sector. Media is helping the state to get more venture in the retail sector to induce more consumer.

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